
ADDICTIONS: PSYCHIATRIC AND PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO BEHAVIORAL AND PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCE DEPENDENCE

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ABSTRACT: Relevance. According to experts in the field of addictology, any stimulus capable of influencing an individual's mental activity can contribute to the development of addiction. Repetitive patterns of behavior, when gradually taking on a compulsory nature, are considered addictive disorders. Research indicates that substance-related addictions and behavioral addictions share certain diagnostic features while also exhibiting specific clinical and psychological differences. The primary aim of this study is to systematically analyze and compare existing psychiatric and psychological approaches to these forms of addiction. Methods: The study examined similarities and differences among various theoretical concepts related to substance-related and behavioral addictions. Collected data were systematically organized, categorized into thematic groups, and analyzed using content analysis methods, resulting in the identification of key topics and conceptual frameworks. Results: Behavioral addictions, such as internet addiction, share several similarities with substance dependence; however, the dependence in behavioral addictions is directed not toward a chemical substance but toward a specific behavior or the emotional experience associated with it. Classical physical withdrawal symptoms typically observed in substance dependence are usually absent in behavioral addictions. Nevertheless, many researchers emphasize that individuals with behavioral addictions exhibit characteristic symptoms and may experience clinical signs and functional impairments comparable to those seen in alcohol and drug dependence, as well as in other compulsive behaviors. Conclusion: Similar to strategies for preventing substance dependence, targeted prevention programs and specialized educational interventions play a crucial role in the early detection and prevention of addictive behavioral disorders. In particular, educating adolescents about early warning signs of internet addiction facilitates timely identification of the disorder. Effective prevention of behavioral addictions requires the coordinated efforts of governmental authorities, cultural and educational institutions, and parents to monitor internet use and to teach children and adolescents appropriate, safe, and constructive ways of using digital resources.

Keywords: addiction; substance dependence; addictive behavior; prevention

АДДИКЦИИ: ПСИХИАТРИЧЕСКИЕ И ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ПОВЕДЕНЧЕСКОЙ И ПСИХОАКТИВНОЙ ЗАВИСИМОСТЯМ

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АННОТАЦИЯ: Введение. По мнению специалистов в области аддиктологии, любой стимул, способный влиять на психическую деятельность человека, может способствовать развитию зависимости. Повторяющиеся модели поведения, постепенно приобретая обязательный характер, рассматриваются как аддиктивные расстройства. Исследования показывают, что зависимости, связанные с психоактивными веществами, и поведенческие зависимости имеют ряд общих диагностических признаков, при этом демонстрируют определённые клинические и психологические различия. Основная цель данного исследования - систематически проанализировать и сравнить существующие психиатрические и психологические подходы к этим формам зависимости. Методы: В исследовании были выявлены сходства и различия между различными теоретическими концепциями, касающимися зависимостей, связанных с психоактивными веществами, и поведенческих зависимостей. Собранные данные были систематизированы, распределены по тематическим группам и проанализированы с использованием метода контент-анализа, что позволило выделить ключевые темы и концептуальные рамки. Результаты: Поведенческие зависимости, такие как интернет-зависимость, имеют несколько схожих черт с зависимостью от веществ; однако зависимость при поведенческих аддикциях направлена не на химическое вещество, а на конкретное поведение или эмоциональный опыт, связанный с ним. Классические физические симптомы абстиненции, обычно наблюдаемые при зависимости от веществ, как правило, отсутствуют при поведенческих аддикциях. Тем не менее, многие исследователи отмечают, что у лиц с поведенческими зависимостями проявляются характерные симптомы и могут развиваться клинические признаки и функциональные нарушения, сопоставимые с теми, что наблюдаются при алкогольной и наркотической зависимости, а также при других навязчивых формах поведения. Заключение: аналогично стратегиям профилактики зависимости от психоактивных веществ, целевые профилактические программы и специальные образовательные мероприятия играют важную роль в раннем выявлении и предотвращении аддиктивных поведенческих расстройств. В частности, обучение подростков ранним признакам интернет-зависимости способствует своевременному выявлению данного расстройства. Эффективная профилактика поведенческих зависимостей требует координированных усилий государственных органов, культурно-образовательных учреждений и родителей по контролю за использованием интернета и обучению детей и подростков правильному, безопасному и целесообразному использованию цифровых ресурсов.

Ключевые слова: зависимость; зависимость от психоактивных веществ; аддиктивное поведение; профилактика

ADDIKSIYALAR: XULQ-ATVORIY VA PSIXOAKTIV MODDALARGA QARAMLIKKA PSIXIATRIK HAMDA PSIXOLOGIK YONDASHUVLAR

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ANNOTATSIYA: Kirish. Addiktologiya sohasi mutaxassislarining fikricha, shaxsning psixik faoliyatiga ta’sir ko‘rsatishga qodir bo‘lgan har qanday stimulyator addiksiya rivojlanishiga sabab bo‘lishi mumkin. Takroriy xulq-atvor shakllari vaqt o‘tishi bilan majburiy xarakter kasb etganda, ular addiktiv buzilish sifatida baholanadi. Ilmiy tadqiqotlar psixoaktiv moddalarga bog‘liq addiksiyalar bilan xulq-atvor addiksiyalari o‘rtasida umumiy diagnostik belgilar mavjudligini, shu bilan birga ularning klinik va psixologik jihatdan muayyan farqlarga ega ekanligini ko‘rsatmoqda. Mazkur tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi addiksiyaning ushbu shakllariga nisbatan mavjud psixiatrik va psixologik yondashuvlarni tizimli tahlil qilish hamda ularni taqqoslashdan iborat. Usullar: Tadqiqot doirasida psixoaktiv modda bilan bog‘liq va xulq-atvor addiksiyalariga oid turli nazariy konsepsiyalar o‘rtasidagi o‘xshashlik va farqlar aniqlandi. Olingan ilmiy ma’lumotlar tizimlashtirildi, tematik guruhlariga ajratildi va kontent-tahlil usuli yordamida tahlil qilindi, natijada asosiy mavzular hamda konseptual tushunchalar ajratib olindi. Natijalar: Internetga qaramlik kabi xulq-atvor addiksiyalari psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik bilan bir qator umumiy jihatlarga ega bo‘lib, biroq bunda qaramlik kimyoviy modda emas, balki muayyan xulq-atvor yoki ushbu faoliyat bilan bog‘liq emotsional kechinmalarga yo‘naltirilganligi bilan farqlanadi. Modda qaramligida kuzatiladigan an’anaviy jismoniy abstinents belgilar xulq-atvor addiksiyalarida, odatda, aniqlanmaydi. Shunga qaramay, ko‘plab tadqiqotchilar xulq-atvor addiksiyasiga chalingan shaxslarda alkogol va gilyohvand moddalarga qaramlikda, shuningdek boshqa majburiy xulq-atvor buzilishlarida kuzatiladigan psixologik va ijtimoiy oqibatlariga o‘xshash klinik belgilar hamda funksional buzilishlar rivojlanishini qayd etadilar. Xulosa: Psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlikning oldini olishga qaratilgan profilaktik strategiyalar singari, addiktiv xulq-atvor buzilishlarini barvaqt aniqlash va oldini olishda maqsadli profilaktik dasturlar hamda maxsus ta’limiy chora-tadbirlar muhim ahamiyatga ega. Xususan, o‘smirlarni internetga qaramlikning erta ogohlantiruvchi belgilari haqida xabardor qilish ushbu buzilishlarni erta aniqlashga xizmat qiladi. Xulq-atvor addiksiyalarining oldini olishda davlat tuzilmalari, madaniy-ma’rifiy muassasalar va ota-onalarning hamkorlikdagi faoliyati, internetdan foydalanishni oqilona nazorat qilish hamda bolalar va o‘smirlarga undan to‘g‘ri, foydali va maqsadga muvofiq foydalanish ko‘nikmalarini shakllantirish muhim hisoblanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: addiksiya; psixoaktiv moddalarga qaramlik; addiktiv xulq-atvor; profilaktika.

Introduction. The concept of addiction is complex and, in many respects, controversial. The term “addiction” generally refers to an individual’s dependence on a specific substance or activity, which significantly affects their psychological and social functioning [1]. Traditionally, addiction has been

associated only with psychoactive substances such as alcohol, nicotine, and heroin; however, recent research indicates that any source capable of stimulating an individual—whether a behavior or an activity—can also lead to addiction.

Until recently, “non-substance-related behavioral addiction” was not listed as a separate category in internationally recognized diagnostic manuals, namely DSM-IV-TR (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders) and ICD-10 (International Classification of Diseases) [2,3]. However, behaviors such as gambling, substance abuse, computer gaming, or internet chatting, when transitioning from habit to compulsive behavior, are considered forms of behavioral addiction [4].

Peele highlighted that behavioral addiction can exist even in the absence of substances. According to him, individuals with addiction are dependent on a specific set of experiences, and their reactions are not limited to a particular chemical substance [4]. Building on this idea, some researchers have suggested that addiction does not necessarily involve the misuse of chemical substances [5,6].

The term “addiction” is often used to describe excessive behaviors such as gambling, video gaming, eating disorders, sports and physical exercise, media consumption, sexual addiction, pathological workaholicism, and compulsive criminal behavior [7-14]. Although these behavioral addictions are not associated with chemical substances, researchers have noted that their core symptoms resemble those of substance-related addiction [15]. Diagnosing behavioral addiction requires the presence of functional impairments in work, social relationships, or other social contexts [16].

Some experts classify behavioral addictions as passive (e.g., watching television) or active (e.g., computer gaming), often involving reinforcing features that promote addictive tendencies [17-20]. Therefore, studying behavioral addictions in depth and understanding their developmental mechanisms is crucial for supporting mental health and developing effective prevention strategies.

Purpose of the study. The aim of this study is to examine substance-related and behavioral addictions from psychiatric and psychological perspectives, identify their similarities and differences, and analyze opportunities to improve preventive measures for early detection and intervention of behavioral addictions, such as internet addiction.

Materials and methods. This is a descriptive study using content analysis. Scientific literature from 2020-2025 was reviewed to identify similarities and differences between theoretical perspectives on substance-related and behavioral addictions. The collected data were coded, categorized by topics, discussed, and the main issues and conceptual themes were extracted.

Results and discussion. The study found that while substance-related and behavioral addictions share diagnostic symptoms, there are notable differences. Behavioral addictions such as gambling, overeating, television compulsion, and internet addiction resemble substance-related addictions, except that the individual is addicted to the behavior or the feelings produced by the activity, rather than a substance. The main characteristics of behavioral addictions were identified based on Goodman and Griffiths’ criteria.

Behavioral addictions do not exhibit the physical signs associated with substance addiction. Depression, substance dependence or withdrawal, social anxiety, and lack of social support were identified as psychopathological factors contributing to behavioral addiction.

According to the Davis model, Urzack emphasized that individuals with behavioral addictions are often fatigued, depressed, lonely, and shy, and may be prone to other types of addiction. Young indicated

that individuals with behavioral addiction experience similar clinical and psychosocial consequences as those with substance addiction and other obsessive behaviors.

From a neurobiological perspective, behavioral addictions, although indirectly affecting brain neurotransmitter systems, can serve as reinforcers comparable to pharmacological substances. Recent research confirms the presence of common mechanisms in both behavioral and substance-related addictions. Excessive behaviors such as compulsive shopping, sports, pathological gambling, computer gaming, and internet use produce reward sensations via biochemical processes in the body and have addictive potential.

Individuals with behavioral addiction exhibit symptoms such as craving, excessive engagement, psychological and physical withdrawal, loss of control, tolerance (expansion of behavior range), and experiencing expected psychotropic effects. The high comorbidity between behavioral and substance-related addictions suggests similar etiological mechanisms. Accordingly, excessive behaviors that cause harm to individuals can be classified as behavioral addictions.

From a psychological and psychiatric perspective, behavioral addictions include anxiety, depression, obsessive thoughts, isolation, affective disorders, social relationship difficulties, academic failure, neglect of work or personal responsibilities, and mental or physical discomfort. Reducing or stopping the behavior may lead to fatigue, decreased physical activity, changes in sleep and eating patterns, impatience, aggression, and sexual disturbances. Risk factors have biological bases, and some can be effectively treated with SSRIs. Cognitive-behavioral therapy is also effective in treating substance use disorders, emotional disorders, and eating disorders.

Treatment of behavioral addiction should consider four key aspects: the individual's prior psychopathology, differential reinforcement, maladaptive cognitions, and social support networks. Specialists must be aware of the psychological problems arising from addictive behaviors, including anxiety, depression, aggression, and academic or occupational dissatisfaction.

Conclusions. Similar to programs aimed at preventing substance-related addiction, specialized educational measures are crucial for preventing internet addiction, raising adolescents' awareness, and facilitating early detection. Parents should inform children about the negative consequences and moral implications of excessive internet use, monitor their online activity, and teach proper, productive usage. Behavioral science specialists can help adolescents understand the underlying causes of their internet habits and reintegrate previous activities into daily life. Identifying and addressing risk factors such as loneliness, stress, depression, and anxiety is essential. State authorities and cultural institutions should promote healthy and purposeful internet use, especially among adolescents. While filtering may be a temporary measure, strengthening religious beliefs and spirituality can help normalize appropriate internet use in society.

References:

1. Akramov S., Buronov J., Turayev B. Clinical forms, course and treatment methods of maniacal-depressive psychosis disease //Modern Science and Research. – 2025. – T. 4. – №. 1. – C. 176-185.
2. Buriboyevna A. D. et al. Hemorrhagic stroke-symptoms and treatment //Western European Journal of Medicine and Medical Science. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 7. – C. 35-38.
3. Erdanovna R. F. Et al. Dorivor osimliklarning yurak glikozidlari sifatida tasiri va qollanilishi //Ijodkor o'qituvchi. – 2025. – T. 4. – №. 46. – C. 71-73.

4. Hamdullo o'g'li J. H., Temirpulotovich T. B. Features of the Clinical Course of Post-Traumatic Epilepsy, Psychiatric and Neurosurgical Approaches //International Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience and Psychology. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 8-14.
5. Hamidullayevna X. D., Temirpulotovich T. B. Features of psycho-emotional changes in women during pregnancy //Journal of Science in Medicine and Life. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 71-77.
6. Hamidullayevna X. D., Temirpulotovich T. B. Features of psycho-emotional changes in women during pregnancy //Journal of Science in Medicine and Life. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 71-77.
7. Hamidullayevna X. D., Temirpulotovich T. B. Personality and interpersonal relationships of primary school students with hyperactivity disorder of minimal brain dysfunction and attention deficit //International Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience and Psychology. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 22-27.
8. Holdorovna I. M., Temirpulotovich T. B. Analysis of the psychopathological and neurophysiological profile of children left without parental care //Journal of Science in Medicine and Life. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 63-70.
9. Holdorovna I. M., Temirpulotovich T. B. Psychopathological features of long-term endogenous depressions //International Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience and Psychology. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 15-21.
10. Jalilova S. H., Kibriyev K., Turayev B. Contemporary accounts of schizophrenia //Modern Science and Research. – 2025. – T. 4. – №. 1.
11. Kholmurodova D. Et al. Study of the process of obtaining fuel briquettes from production waste //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2024. – T. 508. – C. 07008.
12. Mamadiyarova H., Yusupova S., Raxmanova F. About study of the process of producing defoliant based on sodium chlorate and aminoguanidine phosphate. – 2021.
13. Mustafoev A. I. Et al. Enhancing characteristics of a ceramic product from local raw materials produced on the basis of a large solar device in a non-conventional mode //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 202-210.
14. Mustafoev A. I. Et al. Stabilization Processes Of Ceramic Materials Based On Local Raw Materials Processed In A Solar Device //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 258-265.
15. Mustafoev A. I. Et al. Technological features of the selection of local raw materials to be prepared on the basis of a large solar device //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 266-273.
16. Rotanov A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 267-272.
17. Sadullayeva R., Sharafova M., Turayev B. The development of psychoses in infectious diseases and their clinical features //Modern Science and Research. – 2025. – T. 4. – №. 1. – C. 124-129.
18. Sedenkova M. et al. Basic principles of organizing gerontopsychiatric assistance and their advantages //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 63-69.
19. Sedenkova M. et al. Features of primary and secondary cognitive functions characteristic of dementia with delirium //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 56-62.
20. Sharapova D. et al. Clinical and socio-economic effectiveness of injectable long-term forms of atypical antipsychotics in schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 290-295.